

INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

ISSUE 6, PART 1 / JUNE 2026

 Acceptance of papers

**Acceptance of
papers**
Published monthly

Topics
economics,
technology, social
sciences

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THE SCIENTIFIC-POPULAR ELECTRONIC
JOURNAL **"INNOVATION SCIENCE AND
TECHNOLOGY"** HAS BEEN REGISTERED
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AGENCY FOR INFORMATION AND MASS
COMMUNICATIONS (AOKA) OF THE
REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN, EFFECTIVE
FROM OCTOBER 9, 2024.

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CONTENTS

BUDGETING BASED ON THE BALANCED SCORECARD SYSTEM IN STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT ACCOUNTING

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Annotatsiya. Xo'jalik yurituvchi subyektlarning strategik boshqaruv hisobida muvozanatlashgan ko'rsatkichlar tizimi asosida budjetlashtirish masalalari tadqiq etilgan. Budjetlashtirish jarayonining strategik maqsadlar bilan uyg'unligini ta'minlash mexanizmlari yoritilgan hamda “Navoiy kon-metallurgiya kombinati” AJning strategik xaritalari tahlil qilingan. Shuningdek, natijaga yo'naltirilgan budjetlashtirishning blok-sxemasi ishlab chiqilib, uning strategik boshqaruv samaradorligini oshirishdagi ahamiyati asoslab berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: strategik boshqaruv hisobi, xo'jalik yurituvchi subyektlar, muvozanatlashgan ko'rsatkichlar tizimi, budjetlashtirish, strategik xarita, boshqaruv hisobi, strategik vazifa, natijadorlik, moliyaviy ko'rsatkichlar.

Аннотация. Исследованы вопросы бюджетирования на основе системы сбалансированных показателей в стратегическом управленческом учёте хозяйствующих субъектов. Раскрыты механизмы обеспечения взаимосвязи процесса бюджетирования со стратегическими целями организации, а также проведён анализ стратегических карт АО «Навоийский горно-металлургический комбинат». Кроме того, разработана блок-схема результативно-ориентированного бюджетирования и обосновано её значение в повышении эффективности стратегического управления.

Ключевые слова: стратегический управленческий учёт, хозяйствующие субъекты, система сбалансированных показателей, бюджетирование, стратегическая карта, управленческий учёт, стратегическая задача, результативность, финансовые показатели.

Abstract. Issues of budgeting based on the Balanced Scorecard system in the strategic management accounting of business entities are examined. The mechanisms for aligning budgeting processes with strategic objectives are discussed, and the strategic maps of JSC “Navoi Mining and Metallurgical Company” are analyzed. In addition, a results-oriented budgeting framework is developed, and its role in enhancing the effectiveness of strategic management is substantiated.

Keywords: strategic management accounting, business entities, Balanced Scorecard, budgeting, strategic map, management accounting, strategic objective, performance, financial indicators.

INTRODUCTION

The effective organization and management of strategic management accounting in business entities largely depend on the proper use of interrelated elements that form an integrated system. Two key components at the core of strategic management accounting, namely the Balanced Scorecard and budgeting, ensure the implementation of the goals and strategies established for a business entity. These elements play a crucial role in achieving the objectives of strategic management accounting.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The theoretical and practical aspects of the effective organization and management of strategic management accounting in business entities have been extensively examined by foreign scholars such as A. Upchurch, E. Atkinson, R. Banker, P. Brewer, K. Drury, K. Ward, and C. Horngren in their scientific works [1].

Research on strategic management accounting has also been conducted by scholars from the CIS countries, including V.B. Ivashkevich, V.E. Kerimov, I.G. Kondratova, and V.F. Paliy [2].

Certain theoretical and practical aspects of organizing strategic management accounting have been addressed in the scientific works of Uzbek scholars, including A.A. Abduganiyev, N.B. Abdusalamova, U.U. Kostaev, A.Kh. Pardaev, B.A. Khasanov, A.A. Khashimov, and I.K. Giyasov. However, there are still very few studies devoted to the practical organization of strategic management accounting as an integrated system

within business entities [3].

As the Russian scholar V.E. Kerimov noted: "There are practically no published works on strategic management accounting in our national educational and scientific literature" [4].

Another economist, N.M. Blazhenkova, expressed a similar opinion, emphasizing that issues related to the organization and implementation of strategic management accounting in business practice remain highly relevant. In this regard, insufficient attention is often paid to its essence, and in most cases it continues to be considered merely a component of management accounting [5].

According to A.Kh. Paradaev, one of the leading Uzbek scholars, "...in countries with developed market economies, strategic management accounting is recognized as a branch of management accounting that provides information for strategic decision-making. Within the framework of strategic management accounting, a comprehensive analysis of all areas of an economic entity's activities is conducted" [6].

Foreign scholars Mark DeFond and Jinshuai Hu proposed improving management mechanisms through the analysis of the relationship between production revenues, production costs, and cash flows from sales within the strategic management process [7].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study is based on an analysis of economists' views regarding budgeting founded on the Balanced Scorecard system within strategic management. The research methodology includes observation of budgeting processes, analysis of socio-economic conditions, examination of the structural framework of the Balanced Scorecard system, comparative analysis, and synthesis of the obtained results. The conclusions and recommendations presented in the study are based on the findings derived from these research methods.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Scientific research conducted in this field shows that the organization of strategic management accounting has not yet been fully implemented in the majority of business entities operating in various sectors of the national economy, regardless of their ownership form or field of activity. As noted by scholars, insufficient scientific attention has been paid to the two core components of strategic management accounting, namely the Balanced Scorecard system and budgeting. In other words, the practical application of the Balanced Scorecard system and budgeting, as well as several organizational and managerial aspects of strategic management accounting in business entities, still require further development and implementation.

The results of scientific research indicate that in countries with developed market economies, the Balanced Scorecard system is widely used as an effective tool for organizing and implementing strategic management accounting. The model developed by R. Kaplan and D. Norton includes the following four perspectives: 1 – Financial; 2 – Customer; 3 – Internal Business Processes; 4 – Learning and Growth.

Economists also propose including indicators related to **social significance** within this framework. Research findings show that, depending on the specific conditions, opportunities, mission, and strategy of a business entity, additional indicators may be incorporated, including educational programs, scientific research and development, financial indicators, social programs, education, and informatization. It should be noted that the indicators included in the Balanced Scorecard system should not function independently; rather, they should operate as an integrated model serving a common goal and a unified mission (Table 1).

Table 1
Balanced Scorecard System of a Business Entity¹

Strategic tasks	Indicators
Prospects of "Finance".	
Improvement of financial and economic mechanisms	Effective use of available resources, optimization of cash flows, development and implementation of effective investment projects, increasing profitability, choosing the optimal structure of expenses, diversifying activities.
"Customer" prospects	
Meeting customer demand	Using modern and "customer-oriented" methods of pricing products, identifying priorities for long-term cooperation with customers, improving the quality of the products and services offered and achieving brand status - having your own brand.
Perspectives of "internal business processes".	

¹ Compiled by the author.

Strategic tasks	Indicators
Improvement of technological processes and attraction of innovations	Introducing modern production standards in all areas of activity, purposeful management of the system of working with suppliers and buyers, introducing a "single value chain" model into this system, using modern technologies in all processes and introducing innovations.
"Education and growth" prospects	
Development of human, organizational and informational capital	The level of knowledge and skills of professional personnel, corporate culture and corporate performance and labor discipline, information systems, networks and databases, appreciation of knowledge and the formation of management culture and style
Perspectives of "social importance"	
Improving the quality of education and knowledge	Appreciation of knowledge components, stimulation of knowledge and skill improvement, stimulation of information technologies, specialists who know foreign languages, development and implementation of development programs in this regard.

The subject of the Balanced Scorecard system is the determination of specific parameters for the processes of organizing strategic management accounting in business entities, while its object is the management of the implementation of these indicators.

The Balanced Scorecard system serves as a long-term strategic management tool for business entities. Through the Balanced Scorecard model, managers can assess the extent to which the value, price, and quality of their products meet current customer demands, as well as determine future performance targets. In conditions of intense competition, this model helps identify directions for mobilizing existing capabilities and developing investment attraction programs.

Strategic maps are developed to ensure a link between the key elements of an organization's strategy and the Balanced Scorecard system designed to implement it. They also facilitate feedback, performance monitoring, and deviation analysis.

Figure 1 presents the main elements reflecting the strategy of JSC "Navoi Mining and Metallurgical Company" and highlights the factors that reveal the essence of these elements as well as the strategic maps formed on their basis.

Figure 1. Overview of strategic cards of JSC "Navoi Mining and Metallurgical Company"

In strategic maps, balanced indicators are grouped according to strategic perspectives. This, in turn, ensures that the strategy of a business entity is divided into interconnected components and creates opportunities for the effective implementation of each strategic direction.

One of the most important features of the Balanced Scorecard system is that all structural divisions of a business entity participate in implementing their respective components of the target strategy. As a result, the entire organization works toward common strategic objectives and moves in the same direction.

The use of budgeting in strategic management accounting has several distinctive features. First, budgeting provides a systematic approach to management. Second, budgeting encompasses all four management functions, namely planning, organizing, motivating, and controlling. Third, budgeting serves as an important management function in the operation of a business entity: clarifying objectives, planning resources, evaluating performance, motivating employees through performance assessment, and monitoring the achievement of established targets.

Budgeting determines the strategic goals of a business entity, develops performance indicators for achieving these goals, and expresses planned activities in financial terms (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Results-oriented budgeting flowchart ².

2 Compiled by the author.

The role of budgeting not only in strategic management accounting but also in accounting in general has been examined by many economists. In particular, A.V. Alferi emphasized that budgeting in strategic management accounting represents “the ability to predict the results of economic activity in advance”.

A.K. Gidilia, fully supporting the view that budgeting is aimed at forecasting the results of planned activities, added: “...even if it is impossible to predict and eliminate all adverse situations and factors affecting economic activity, it is important to foresee the possibility of such effects in advance and plan measures to minimize their impact”.

Y.V. Sokolov emphasized that “...factors that have already occurred are of limited relevance in accounting, whereas current factors require continuous analysis, and the most important aspect of a properly organized accounting system is its orientation toward the future”.

The views of these scholars indicate that budgeting is one of the most important instruments for ensuring future-oriented management and sustainable development.

Based on the above considerations, it can be concluded that budgeting within the strategic management accounting system performs the following important functions:

determines the future financial and economic plans of a business entity, defines financial objectives, establishes specific performance indicators for all activities and components, and sets deadlines for their implementation;

coordinates the activities of structural units included in the management system;

provides operational control over budget implementation, identifies deviations from budget parameters, analyzes their causes, and supplies the information necessary for making appropriate management decisions;

monitors the effectiveness of individual programs implemented within structural units;

ensures the functioning of the system of financial responsibility and accountability for performance results, evaluates the contribution of individual structural units to strengthening the financial position of the business entity, and provides a basis for financial incentives for employees and specialists.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the results of the scientific research, a critical analysis of the views of existing economic schools on this issue, and a generalization of their approaches, it can be concluded that budgeting within the strategic management accounting system of business entities performs the following functions:

- budgeting of key performance indicators to ensure the achievement of the strategic goals of a business entity;
- budgeting of business processes aimed at achieving the strategic objectives of the business entity;
- integration of the budgeting system with financial and investment responsibility centers in order to ensure accountability, responsibility, motivation, and performance-based incentives;
- budgeting of investment projects, capital expenditures, and technological modernization programs;
- budgeting of the activities of structural units based on strategic performance indicators developed for their long-term development.

The implementation of the Balanced Scorecard system and budgeting within strategic management accounting can significantly transform the nature of the accounting system. As a result, the system becomes more dynamic and enables the assessment of not only quantitative and qualitative indicators but also the prospects of future development. This, in turn, serves as an important factor in achieving sustainable competitive advantages in both domestic and international markets, particularly under conditions of increasing competition driven by globalization processes.

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Proofreader: Zokir ALIBEKOV
Layout and Designer: Oloviddin Sobir ugli

2026. № 6

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